

**Natural products from Octocoral
*Carijoa (Telesto) riisei***

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Abstract

A number of natural products found in various octocorals have shown promise for drug-design and pharmaceutical applications. Two classes of chemical compounds, punaglandins and pregnane steroids, from dichloromethane extracts of soft octocoral, *Carijoa (Telesto) riisei* have been investigated throughout this research. The original source of isolated punaglandins was collected in Hawaii and demonstrated anti-inflammatory and antitumor activity. *T. riisei* was recently collected in Clearwater Beach, Florida and posses similar chemistry, including punaglandins and steroids, as those previously studied despite considerable variation between respective ecosystems. The sample of coral was extracted and separated in a series of chromatographic methods monitored via ¹H-NMR guided fractionation. It has been demonstrated that known punaglandins exist in *T. riisei* from Clearwater Beach, Florida. and is hypothesized that novel compounds exist within samples of *T. riisei* due to variation in habitat amongst the coral samples from Florida and Hawaii.

I. Introduction

1. Natural Products

Natural products chemistry has been an area of intrigue since the origins of organic chemistry for a number of reasons.¹ Many chemists have looked to the study of natural products to discover materials for drug design, a field of study that has been overwhelmingly dominated by synthetic chemists in recent years. Natural products chemistry has been integral in answering some of the major questions of academia, underlies revolutionary advancements in medicine, and even played a role in industrial and commercial product development. It is without question that our lives have been significantly impacted by the tedious work of organic chemists, and specifically natural product chemists, of the past. Before the 1960s most discoveries in natural products chemistry originated from studying terrestrial organisms due to a lack of technology to begin exploring what organisms of aquatic environments were able to offer to the field¹. Since the advancement of technology, marine natural products has grown into a field of study all its own with many important discoveries to be made.

Natural products chemistry focuses on the study of secondary metabolites, including polyketides and fatty acids, terpenoids and steroids, phenylpropanoids, alkaloids, specialized amino acids, as well specialized carbohydrates.² Secondary metabolites differ from primary metabolites in that they are not in every cell and do not play a central role in cellular functions such as reproduction or division. However, secondary metabolites play an important role in other physiological functions in organisms and often mediate interactions between organisms, making secondary metabolite particularly interesting for biochemists, chemical ecologists, and

chemotaxonomists. Secondary metabolites serve a number of functions in organisms, but some of the most studied phenomenon includes chemical defense and cell signaling. Estimates show that over 40% of medicines originated exclusively from the study of natural products.³

Groundbreaking discoveries in natural products include Taxol, isolated from the bark of *Taxus brevifolia* and an effective cancer treatment,⁴ and Penicillin, used as an antibiotic around the world.

Such as with Penicillin, newly discovered secondary metabolites can be used as precursors to the discovery of other active forms of compounds. Although this often seems effective, there are fallbacks associated with this method. Many pathogenic microorganisms have adaptive capabilities and often gain resistance to a drug. This process can often be efficient enough for microorganisms to become immune to an entire class of compounds. For example, a class of pharmaceutical drugs, quinolones, has shown an extensive number of applications in medicine such as antimalarial, antibacterial and antitumor activity³ is understood that the quinolones have a mechanism of action at the genetic level and it is believed that exposing microorganism to such a drug can ultimately increase microorganism quorum sensing. This may result in accelerated proliferation and enhanced adaptive abilities, ultimately favoring the spread of resistance.³ Although some of the quinolone drugs are effective, they have the potential to cause more harm than necessary by increasing the spread of resistance. The quinolones are also thought to have unspecific cytotoxic properties that lower quinolone drug utility in a clinical setting. Instead of continuing to modify current drugs, natural products chemists aim to discover new organic molecules, and often novel scaffolds of bioactive compounds, that may be useful as pharmaceuticals or as precursors to pharmaceuticals in order to avoid the use of potentially harmful drugs such as quinolones.

The purpose of this study was to identify potential secondary metabolites that existed within a sample of *Telestoa* collected at Clearwater Reef, Florida and to understand the application of such findings on further drug discovery research and pharmaceutical design. Particular focus was placed on the discovery of punaglandins as they have not been reported in samples of *Telestoa* in any locations other than Hawaii.

2. Taxonomy

Telestoa is classified into the Phylum Cnidaria, which consists of exclusively aquatic organisms, which possess intrinsic nematocysts and often toxic secretory products termed cnida.⁵ The cnidarians are distinguished further according to morphological structures. *T. riisei* is classified into the class Anthozoa, having only a polyp form rather than also possessing a medusa form like the Hydrozoans, and Scyphozoans.⁵ Anthozoa is further divided into subclasses Hexacorallia and Octocorallia based upon morphological features. Octocorals possess a polyp with eight branched tentacles rather than six such as in the Hexacorals. Corals of the genus *Telestoa* have eight white tentacles, giving it a distinguished appearance responsible for the nickname “snowflake coral”. Taxonomists have faced difficulty distinguishing separate species of the genus *Telestoa* as with many cnidarians and in some instances have looked to chemical ecologists for further investigation.⁶ Taxonomists are currently divided as to the correct classification of *T. riisei*. One system classifies the coral as a member of the Clavulariidae family in order Stolonifera, whereas another system of a separate family, Telesiidae in the order Telestacae, is created to accommodate the diverse coral. Taxonomists hoped to distinguish the geographically diverse samples of *Telestoa* according to the finding of chemical ecologists, but the coral produces a number of natural products that vary among the samples making it difficult to classify the coral in any further detail.⁶

3. Chemical Ecology and Distribution

Soft corals have gained attention from chemists in the past 50 years because they possess substantially more organic matter than hard corals.⁶ Secondary metabolites are a particularly important area of study for chemical ecologists. Toxic and non-toxic secondary metabolites have been found to affect predator-prey interactions, organisms habitation patterns, and spatial competition.⁷ Chemists have also investigated marine invertebrates such as soft corals to better understand chemical communication, biosynthesis, reproduction, evolutionary patterns, and fouling.⁸ *Telesto* is considered to be a fouling coral and even invasive in some ecosystems. Until recently, only one small nudibranch, *Tritonia wellsi*, had been reported as a predator in any colony of *Telesto*. In 2007, two new predators, both nudibranchs, have been identified to colonies of Hawaiian *Telesto*- *Tritoniopsis elegans* and *Phyllodesmium poindimiei*,⁹ although no new predators of *Telesto* in other locations have been reported. Understanding the relationship between marine organisms is important to biologists and chemists alike. Sessile corals often sequester secondary metabolites from symbionts, producing undesirable or sometimes toxic substances as a means of defense.¹ *Telesto* lacks symbiotic zooxanthellae although it may have a symbiotic relationship with an orange sponge that is often found overgrowing the exterior of the soft coral.¹ Along with a number of survival techniques such as high fecundity and planktonic larval stage, it is hypothesized that *Telesto* possesses particular secondary metabolites that may reduce predation. *Telesto*'s feeding technique, much like all cnidarians, includes the excretion of cnidia from nematocysts to kill or paralyze zooplankton throughout the water which may then be ingested.¹⁰ *Telesto* was initially investigated in Hawaii. Since, the coral has been reported in Caribbean waters from Florida to Brazil, and Micronesia, as well as dispersed widely among the shallow water ecosystems in much of the Hawaiian Islands. The chemistry of *Telesto* has been

studied in each of the reported locations providing valuable chemo-ecological data. Samples collected in varying locations have demonstrated diversity in natural products. Samples of *Telesto* from the Indo-Pacific demonstrated an interesting array of natural products including some chlorinated pregnane steroid derivatives, as well as Carijenone¹¹— a compound having strikingly similar structural similarities to the punaglandins. Sterols and similar pregnane steroid derivatives exist in the Hawaiian, Brazilian, Micronesian, and now Floridian *Telesto*. Cytotoxic amides have been observed only in Brazilian *Telesto*,⁶ and the punaglandins had only been reported in the Hawaiian samples, and samples from Papua New Guinea¹ until this study. Interestingly, predator to *Telesto*- *T. wellsi*- collected in Papua New Guinea was found to contain the same punaglandins extracted from the coral samples,¹ demonstrating sequestration.

4. Pregnane Steroids

Steroid Biosynthesis

Although many marine invertebrates acquire steroid metabolites from dietary consumption, it is believed that soft corals catabolize these natural products as well. Elucidation of biosynthetic pathways underlying the production of sterols and pregnane steroids has taken form in experiments of radioactive labeling.¹² One of the major radioactive substrates utilized in biosynthetic studies by Goad (1981) was ¹⁴C-acetate. The substrate was incorporated into the organism's reservoir of acetyl-CoA by thiokinase. The activity of Hydroxymethylglutaryl CoA (HMG-CoA) reductase is key in understanding the biosynthesis of steroids, as it is responsible for producing mevalonic acid.¹³ Radiolabelled Lanosterol was demonstrated as an intermediate in the production of cholesterol in many mammals and marine invertebrates via the mevalonate pathway. Thus, steroids in marine invertebrates are derived from a mevalonic or non-mevalonic

pathways that result in terpenes, although research by Goad (1981) suggests that the mavalonic pathway is a preferred route by marine invertebrates. Research is constantly underway to better understand the exact enzymes involved in the structures characteristic of steroids in marine invertebrates.¹⁴

Samples of Pregnane steroids from *Telesto* located on the Brazilian coast have been most thoroughly investigated for bioactivity. Crude extracts from samples produced 75 % growth inhibition for MC7 (breast tumor), HCT8 (colon tumor), and B16 (murine melanoma) cell lines at a concentration of 125 µg/mL.¹⁵ Samples were purified further, resulting in Steroid **1** (18-acetoxypregnane) and a pregnane analog deacetylated at position 18 (1,4,20-pregnatrien-3-one). The purified steroids were shown to inhibit the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Trypanosoma cruzi*, and *Leishmania braziliensis*. Steroid **1** showed an increased inhibition of *Leishmania* and cytotoxicity compared to the deacetylated version.¹⁵

5. Punaglandins

Eicosanoid biosynthesis

The biosynthesis of punaglandins has not received adequate investigation, but it may be assumed that the mechanisms of punaglandin biosynthesis are markedly similar to the prostaglandins (PGs) and thus the biosynthetic pathways underlying fatty acid oxidation in invertebrates. The vast majority of research on PG biosynthesis investigates enzyme activity proceeding arachidonic acid synthesis. The proposed biochemical mechanism for arachidonic acid involves a thioester condensation of Acetyl Coenzyme A. Andrew F. Rowley and colleagues at the University of Wales Swansea conducted a thorough review of factors influencing PG biosynthesis in various marine invertebrates. Although it was previously thought

that PG biosynthesis proceeded via lipoxygenase pathway, proceeded by allene oxide synthase activity, current studies indicate that PG biosynthesis is similar to vertebrate PG biosynthesis.¹⁶ Recent cellular and molecular genetic studies indicate that Cyclooxygenase (COX) is required for PG biosynthesis in marine invertebrates, although it appears that the cyclooxygenase responsible is not identical to COX-1 or COX-2 isoenzyme responsible for PG biosynthesis in vertebrates. Further investigation revealed potential biosynthetic mechanisms for unusual methyl esterification and acetylation common amongst the punaglandins, created from otherwise unstable and unlikely intermediates.¹⁶

Beside the functional cyclopentenone ring, each reported punaglandin possesses either a carbon-carbon double bond between carbons 10 and 11 or a C10-11 epoxide ring, as well as C-10 chlorinated. Further investigation would be necessary to understand the biosynthetic pathways responsible for chlorination and epoxidation of proposed PG precursors to punaglandins.

The biosynthesis of the punaglandins is of particular interest due to the novelty of the chlorinated natural products. Valmsen *et al.* argue that understanding the biosynthetic pathways of punaglandins, or the biosynthesis of other invertebrate eicosanoids, may advance our understanding of important metabolic pathways in a number of higher vertebrates. New metabolic pathways, enzymatic functions, and chemical structures in vertebrates have been discovered through the investigation of simpler invertebrates such as corals.¹⁶ It is implied that studying the biosynthetic pathway of corals such as *T. riisei* may also yield comparative and evolutionistic evidence.

Baker and Scheuer originally summarized the biological activity of isolated punaglandins as well as synthetic analogs.¹⁷ The punaglandins showed anti-inflammatory and anti-tumor

activity.^{17,18} L1210 mouse leukemia cells were subject to chemical treatment with punaglandins and similar prostaglandin derivatives, the clauvulones.¹⁹ Punaglandins were shown to be more potent²⁰ but were also too cytotoxic for clinical use, however other synthetic analogs (containing methylthio substituted C-10) were produced that may be promising treatments for osteoporosis.²¹ To further understand the biological activity of the punaglandins, Verbitski *et al.* at the University of Utah investigated a number of cellular pathways where prostaglandins may play a role. They demonstrated that punaglandins inhibit isopeptidase activity and appear more effective than the studied prostaglandins at inhibiting the proliferation of a neoplasm. Furthermore, punaglandins with 7-8 unsaturation such as that in PUG **11** were shown to be more effective at inhibiting a ubiquitin-protease pathway involved in neoplastic development.²²

II. Methods

1. Collection, Extraction and Separation

Samples of *T. riisei* were collected from Clearwater Reef, Florida. A team of divers from the University of South Florida and the Center for Drug Discovery and Innovation lead by Dr. Bill Baker collected the soft octocoral by SCUBA at approximately 25 foot depths. The coral was stored on ice until processed in the laboratory and held in a -20°C freezer.

The frozen specimen was freeze-dried resulting in a mass of 791.69g, before extraction via soxhlet. Four cycles of soxhlet extraction in approximately 3 liters of Dichloromethane. The crude extract was dried using a rotary evaporator, resulting in 8.32g. The crude extract was then dissolved in a solution of 7:3 MeOH to H₂O and partitioned against hexane. Partitioning resulted in an emulsification that was drawn off, dried, and re-dissolved in 7:3 MeOH to H₂O. The solution continued to emulsify and therefore was drawn out of solution, dried, and stored at -

20°C. The extraction method and weights of extracts have been summarized in Figure 1. The partition resulted in 1.80g of the crude aqueous extract, which was analyzed via a 500 MHz Varian nuclear magnetic resonance spectrometer (NMR) equipped with a cryoprobe. The crude aqueous extract was dissolved with silica, dried, and packed into a cartridge for medium pressure liquid chromatography (MPLC). The sample was fractionated by normal phase MPLC. The solvent system utilized for MPLC separation was a gradient beginning with 100% hexane, flowing to 100% ethyl acetate over 20 minutes and remaining at 100% ethyl acetate for 10 minutes, followed by gradient change to 80% ethyl acetate and 20% methanol. The MPLC chromatogram and method may be viewed in Figure 2 (solvent B – EtOAc). The remainder of the experiment was conducted by NMR guided fractionation. MPLC fractions were selected for further investigation based upon data from NMR spectra. MPLC Fraction D (Figure 3- NMR Spectra for fractions C, D, and E) appeared to contain the highest concentration of known punaglandins and had been selected as the focus of investigation for the remainder of the study. Reported compounds were purified by high-pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC) on a semi-preparatory column, followed by a multitude of reverse phased HPLC experiments on an analytical C-18 column.

III. Results

Separation by normal phase HPLC with a Semi-preparatory column resulted in two separate fractions of pure Steroids **1**, and **2**, (Tables 1-2) and four fractions demonstrating patterns of chemical shifts characteristic of the punaglandins which were subject to further purification through analytical HPLC utilizing a reversed phase solvent system of 75% H₂O to 100% MeOH. Separation by reverse phase HPLC yielded known punaglandins¹⁷ **3**, **11**, and **14** and one punaglandin demonstrating unreported chemical shifts (PUG 14 Analog, Table 4).

Steroid 1

Steroid 2

Punaglandin 3

Punaglandin 11

Punaglandin 14

Table 1: ¹H-NMR Data Table for Steroid 1 and 2

Compound				
Position	Steroid 1 Theoretical ²³	Steroid 1 Experimental	Steroid 2 Theoretical ²⁴	Steroid 2* Experimental

H-1	7.06, d	7.02, d	7.04, d	7.03, d
H-2	6.21, dd	6.22, dd	6.22, dd	6.22, dd
H-4	6.06, t	6.06, s	6.06, s	6.05, s
H-6 _a	2.47, m	2.46, m	2.45, ddd	2.44, ddd
H-6 _b	2.36, m	2.36, m	2.35, ddd	2.35, m
H-7 _a	1.95, m	1.95, m	1.96, m	1.92, m
H-7 _b	1.04, m	1.00, m	1.04, m	1.04, m
H-8	1.62, m	1.60, m	1.65, m	1.66, m
H-9	1.06, m	1.08, m	1.06, m	1.05, m
H-11 _a	1.68, m	1.73, m	1.74, m	1.72, m
H-11 _b	-	-	1.57, m	1.58, m
H-12 _a	1.72, m	1.73, m	1.85, ddd	1.83, dt
H-12 _b	1.05, m	1.08, m	1.25, m	1.23, m
H-14	0.99, m	0.87, m	1.00, m	1.02, m
H-15 _a	1.68, m	1.73, m	1.77, m	1.8, m
H-15 _b	1.24, m	1.25, m	1.55, m	1.56, m
H-16 _a	1.78, m	1.75, m	1.7, m	1.7, m
H-16 _b	1.56, m	1.58, m	1.57, m	1.58, m
H-17	1.95, m	1.95, m	1.57, m	1.59, m
H-18	0.65, s	0.85, m	0.7, s	0.68, s
H-19	1.22, s	1.22, s	1.21, s	1.23, m
H-20	5.73, ddd	5.76, ddd	4.83, dq	4.83, dq
H-21 _a	4.98, dd	4.97, dd	1.14, d	1.13, d
H ₃ -21 _b	4.93, dd	4.92, m	-	-
H-OAc	-	-	2.01, s	2.00, s

*Table 1 - Steroid 2 is believed to be partially contaminated with steroid 1, accounting for the lack of resolution about signals upfield of 2ppm. Spectroscopic data obtained from Varian 500MHz NMR spectrometer. *Samples contains mixture *Compound partially impure*

Table 2: ¹³C-NMR Data Table for Steroid 1 and 2

Compound

Position	Steroid 1 Theoretical ²³	Steroid 1 Experimental	Steroid 2 Theoretical ²⁴	Steroid 2* Experimental
1	155.6, d	155.67, d	155.9, d	155.9, d
2	127.6, d	127.54, d	127.5, d	127.48, d
3	186.3, s	186.33, s	186.4, s	186.4, s
4	124.0, d	123.95, d	123.8, d	123.83, d
5	168.5, s	168.85, s	169.3, s	169.23, s
6	32.7, t	32.73, t	32.9, t	32.85, t
7	33.7, t	33.69, t	33.7, t	33.65, t
8	35.6, d	35.64, d	35.4, d	35.42, d
9	52.6, d	52.58, d	52.5, d	52.45, d
10	43.5, s	43.58, s	43.6, s	43.61, s
11	22.5, t	22.5, t	22.8, t	22.8, t
12	32.5, t	32.55, t	38.9, t	38.89, t
13	46.3, s	46.36, s	42.5, s	43.2, s
14	54.3, d	54.33, d	54.8, d	54.89, d
15	24.8, t	24.77, t	25.3, t	25.34, t
16	27.1, t	27.1, t	24.4, t	24.38, t
17	54.6, d	54.6, d	54.8, d	54.85, d
18	62.1, t	62.09, t	12.5, q	12.56, q
19	18.8, q	18.76, q	18.7, q	18.7, q
20	138.8, d	138.77, d	72.7, d	72.67, d
21	114.0, t	114.1, t	19.9, q	19.0, q
C-OAc	171.2, s	171.25, s	170.4, s	170.39, s
COCH ₃	21.1, q	21.1, q	21.5, q	21.48, q
Unidentified	-	-	-	109.98, s

*Compound partially pure

Table 3: ¹H-NMR Data Table for Punaglandin 3 and 11

Compound

Position	PUG3 Theoretical ¹⁷	PUG3 Experimental	PUG11 Theoretical ¹⁷	PUG11* Experimental
H ₂ -2	2.3, m	2.28, m	2.3, m	2.33, m
H ₂ -3	1.6, m	1.6, m	1.6, m	1.66, m
H ₂ -4	1.6, m	1.6, m	1.6, m	1.66, m
H-5	5.18, ddd	5.18, m	5.2, m	5.2, m
H-6	5.61, dd	5.62, m	6.32, dd	6.34, dd
H-7	5.31, dd	5.32, dd	6.07, d	6.09, d
H-8	2.74, d	2.75, d	-	-
H-11	7.26, s	7.26, s	7.2, s	7.2, s
H-13 _a	2.48, dd	2.48, dd	2.56, dd	2.56, dd
H-13 _b	2.40, dd	2.40, dd	2.44, dd	2.41, dd
H-14	5.25, ddd	5.26, m	5.2, m	5.23, m
H-15	5.63, dt	5.62, m	5.57, dt	5.57, m
H ₂ -16	1.95, m	1.99, m	1.97, m	1.97, m
H-17	1.26, m	1.27, m	1.3, m	1.28, m
H-18	1.26, m	1.27, m	1.3, m	1.28, m
H ₂ -19	1.26, m	1.27, m	1.3, m	1.28, m
H ₃ -20	0.85, t	0.87, t	0.87, t	0.86, t
H ₃ -OMe	3.65, s	3.65, s	3.64, s	3.65, s
H ₃ -OAc	2.09, s	2.10, s	2.10, s	2.09, s
H ₃ -OAc	2.06, s	2.07, s	2.03, s	2.03, s
H ₃ -OAc	1.98, s	1.99, s	-	-
H ₃ -OAc	-	-	-	-
H-OH	3.48, s	3.44, s	2.79, s	-

Table 3 - Sample containing Punaglandin **11** is believed to also contain miniscule amounts of either Punaglandin **1** or Punaglandin **3**. Spectroscopic data obtained from Varian 400MHz NMR spectrometer.

*Compound partially pure

Table 4: ¹H-NMR Data Table for Punaglandin 14 and Punaglandin 14 Analog

Compound

Position	PUG14 Theoretical ¹⁷	PUG14* Experimental	PUG14 Theoretical ¹⁷	PUG14 Analog
H ₂ -2	2.3, m	2.32, m	2.3, m	2.33, m
H ₂ -3	1.5, m	1.6, m	1.5, m	1.6, m
H ₂ -4	1.5, m	1.6, m	1.5, m	1.6, m
H-5	5.2, m	5.2, m	5.2, m	5.17, m
H-6	5.97, dd	5.97, dd	5.97, dd	6.03, dd
H-7	6.55, d	6.55, d	6.55, d	6.2, d
H-8	-	-	-	-
H-11	3.95, s	3.95, s	3.95, s	3.94, s
H-13 _a	2.85, dd	2.96, dd	2.85, dd	-
H-13 _b	2.76, dd	2.77, m	2.76, dd	2.75, d
H-14	5.2, m	5.2, m	5.2, m	5.2, m
H-15	5.59, m	5.59, m	5.59, m	5.62, m
H ₂ -16	1.5, m	1.6, m	1.5, m	1.6, m
H-17	1.2, m	1.2, m	1.2, m	1.28, m
H-18	1.2, m	1.2, m	1.2, m	1.28, m
H ₂ -19	1.2, m	1.2, m	1.2, m	1.28, m
H ₃ -20	0.86, t	0.87, m	0.86, t	0.87, t
H ₃ -OMe	3.66, s	3.65, s	3.66, s	3.66, s
H ₃ -OAc	2.09, s	2.09, s	2.09, s	2.09, s
H ₃ -OAc	2.03, s	2.03, s	2.03, s	2.03, s
H ₃ -OAc	-	-	-	-
H ₃ -OAc	-	-	-	-
H-OH	3.55, s	3.64, s	3.55, s	-

Table 4 - Spectroscopic data obtained from Varian 500MHz NMR spectrometer. *Samples contains mixture

Table 5- Percent abundance by mass (dry weight)

Compound	Pure sample	Theoretical Percent Mass	Experimental Percent mass
PUG3	1.1 mg	0.0000019 %	0.0000013%

PUG11*	1.3 mg	0.0000022%	0.0000016%
PUG14*	1.3 mg	0.0000022%	0.0000016%

Values for Table 5 were calculated using the mass of pure sample and dry weight of *T. riisei* collected in Clearwater Reef, Florida. *Compounds partially impure

Steroids were found to be present in considerable concentrations. Characteristic chemical shift patterns for pregnane steroids were noted in multiple MPLC fractions that had not been investigated, leaving percent mass of steroids **1** and **2** in coral to be indeterminate. Known punaglandins believed to be < 0.1% dry weight of coral. Experimental error resulted in a number of unfavorable separations. A total of eleven injections were conducted for NP HPLC on the Semi-preparatory column, each injection averaging 60mg, totaling a mass of 649mg. Injections 5-11 yielded reproducible results. Mass of compounds purified constitutes experimental percent mass. Theoretical percent mass was calculated assuming that concentration of compounds had been homogenous throughout MPLC fraction D and that every NP HPLC injections had identical composition.

IV. Discussion

¹H-NMR and ¹³C-NMR experiments conducted for samples of Steroid **1** and **2** resulted in spectral data found in Tables 1 and 2. Values for ¹H-NMR chemical shifts deviate no more than 0.2ppm from theoretical values, with an average deviation of less than 0.1ppm. ¹³C-NMR data also supports the proposed structures with a maximum deviation from theoretical values of -0.9ppm and an average deviation from theoretical values less than 0.1ppm. Similarity among theoretical and experimentally obtained values indicated that Steroids **1** and **2** have similar, if not the same stereochemistry as that of compounds reported in literature^{23, 24}. Both Steroids **1** and **2** have been previously reported in similar locations. Further studies may include structure elucidation for potentially novel steroids partially purified during analytical HPLC trials that

possess chemical shifts currently unreported. Notable discrepancies include an unexplained ^{13}C -NMR signal for Steroid **2** at 109.98ppm (Table 2) as well as a reported 0.85 multiplet in place of a theoretically proposed 0.67 singlet representing H-18 of Steroid **1** (Table 1). Neither of these findings are believed to be product of contamination, yet they are still unexplained. Further investigation may reveal the nature of these deviations from theoretical data.

Ample evidence has been obtained to support that known punaglandins are present in the samples of *Telesto* collected at Clearwater Reef, Florida. Punaglandin **3** was purified through a number of analytical HPLC experiments, resulting in a compound with virtually identical ^1H -NMR to theoretical data (Table 3). The largest deviation among experimental and theoretical ^1H -NMR data for Punaglandin **3** was 0.04ppm, indicating that the stereochemistry of the investigated compound is similar if not the same as that reported in literature¹⁷. This study marks the first reported evidence that punaglandins are present in considerable concentration in Floridian *Telesto*.

Punaglandin **11** lacks a chemical shift that is indicative of the punaglandins reported in literature¹⁷. There appears to be no signal to account for C-12 hydroxyl or acetate signals that every reported punaglandin possesses. One of the novel aspects of the punaglandins included an oxygenated C-12 with stereochemistry enantiometric to the clavulones.¹⁷ Fractions originally proposed to be Punaglandin **11** lack any signals indicative of a hydroxyl or acetate group at C-12 and appear to have only two acetate signals, which is unreported among studies of the punaglandins. This is a trend that has been noted among a number of HPLC fractions from Floridian *Telesto*. The possibility of an exchangeable proton of a hydroxyl group at position 12 could account for the reduced integration of chemical signals appearing at approximately 3.48ppm, but spectral data does not support structural elements causing such a signal to appear

substantially downfield from the expected 2.79ppm. Although biosynthetic evidence is lacking, it is proposed that samples of *Telesto* collected at Clearwater Reef, Florida contain a number of novel punaglandins that have been deacetylated at one of the commonly acetylated carbon positions, 5, 6, 7, or 12.

Punaglandin **14** has been proposed as a compound present in the sample due to the high similarity between chemical shifts of the reported compound and data obtained in this study- Namely, the distinguishing 3.95 s (only found in punaglandins with epoxides), 5.97 dd, and 6.55 d. Data obtained in this study demonstrate the exact ppm values and splitting patterns for such signals. Punaglandin **14** appears to be contained in a mixture with a compound containing a proton at position 11. Protons producing chemical shifts at 6.2 ppm and 7.63 ppm have not been identified. Slight variation among chemical shifts may be due to different stereochemical arrangements of punaglandin **14**. Further studies in optical rotation and 2 dimensional NMR would be required in order to fully elucidate the proposed structures.

Further studies include collaboration with the Chemodiversity lab's chemical library at the University of South Florida's Center for Drug Discovery and Innovation. Any isolated compounds will be screen against a number of bioassays including neglected and tropical diseases such as leishmaniasis and the ESKAPE pathogens. Steroids with a similarly planar geometry to that of ring 1 of Steroid **1** have shown significant activity against filarial bioassays studied by Dr. Thomas Unnasch and Colleagues at the University of South Florida. After further purification and obtaining complete spectroscopic data, Steroids **1** and **2** may be provided for screening against the filarial parasite.

V. Figures

Figure 1 – Separation Flow Chart of frozen *T. riisei* (Sample CWR13-1)

Figure 1 - separation method was guided by original method utilized in Hawaii by Dr. Baker and colleagues to analyze the composition of *T. riisei*.¹⁷ Alterations include substitution of dichloromethane for petroleum ether during the crude extraction.

Figure 2 – MPLC chromatogram of sample CWR13-1 crude aqueous partition

Figure 2- Fraction chosen for further separation based upon NMR data, fraction D, has been labeled.

Figure 3 – ¹H-NMR spectra of Normal Phase MPLC Fractions C, D, and E overlaid

Figure 3 – Spectra were obtained from 500MHz Varian NMR spectrometer (instrument parameters). MPLC fraction C (blue) demonstrates characteristic pregame steroid chemical shifts between 6-7.1ppm; fraction D (green) demonstrates characteristic pregnane steroid signals as well as punaglandin chemical shifts at 3.65ppm as well as 7.26ppm; fraction E (red) does not demonstrate any defining signals.

Figure 4 – CWR13-1-D: Normal Phase HPLC Chromatogram

Figure 4- Crude separation of CWR13-1-D obtained from Shimadzu HPLC in normal phase.

Figure 5- $^1\text{H-NMR}$ Spectra for Steroid 1

Figure 5 – $^1\text{H-NMR}$ Spectra for Steroid 1 was obtained from 400MHz Varian NMR spectrometer.

Figure 6 - $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ Spectra for Steroid 1

Figure 6- $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ Spectra for Steroid 1 was obtained from 500MHz Varian NMR spectrometer.

Figure 7- $^1\text{H-NMR}$ Spectra for Steroid 1

Figure 7 - $^1\text{H-NMR}$ Spectra for Steroid 1 was obtained from 400MHz Varian NMR spectrometer.

Figure 8- $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ Spectra for Steroid 2

Figure 8- $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ Spectra for Steroid 2 obtained from 500MHz Varian NMR spectrometer.

Figure 9 $^1\text{H-NMR}$ Spectra for Punaglandin **3**

Figure 9 $^1\text{H-NMR}$ Spectra for Punaglandin **3** obtained from 400MHz Varian NMR spectrometer.

Figure 10 $^1\text{H-NMR}$ Spectra for Punaglandin **11**

Figure 10 $^1\text{H-NMR}$ Spectra for Punaglandin **11** 500MHz Varian NMR spectrometer.

VI. References

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